

ENTOMOPATHOGENIC FUNGI (*METARHIZIUM*): CURRENT CHALLENGES, STRATEGIC OPPORTUNITIES, AND FUTURE PROSPECTS FOR SUSTAINABLE PEST MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. *This article discusses the current state, existing challenges, and future development trends of utilizing entomopathogenic fungi (using fungi of the genus *Metarhizium* as an example) as insecticidal, antifungal, and antibacterial biopreparations, as well as biological fertilizers that stimulate plant growth and development. In particular, the prospects for using entomopathogenic fungi in agriculture are evaluated based on several factors, including the primary functional sources of fungal-based microbiological fertilizers (nitrogen fixation, phosphorus mobilization, decomposers of N, P, K, and trace elements), the advantages of producing biological protection agents, the mechanisms of action of entomopathogenic fungi (antagonism, mycoparasitism, hyperparasitism, microbial competition for nutrients among themselves and with insects and nematodes, anabiosis, and endophytism), the impact of entomopathogenic fungi of the genus *Metarhizium* on insect pests, the significance of entomopathogenic fungi as biofertilizers, and the safety aspects of their use. Furthermore, the secondary metabolites of *Metarhizium* fungi, their insecticidal, antibacterial, and antifungal effects, as well as the current market share and prospects of biopesticides in the global pesticide market, are highlighted. Additionally, one of the reliable safety aspects of using entomopathogenic fungi is explained by the fact that the toxin production rate of these fungi under natural conditions is synthesized in very small quantities, rendering them insignificant in terms of toxicity. Nevertheless, from a standpoint of comprehensive safety, it is noted that promoting and widely implementing the use of secondary products of entomopathogenic fungi, rather than their direct primary products, is a safer and more effective approach.*

Keywords: *entomopathogenic fungi, biopesticides, virulence mechanisms, abiotic stress tolerance, sustainable agriculture, integrated pest management.*

Introduction

Global agriculture faces significant threats under the conditions of climate change, including rising average temperatures, soil degradation, water scarcity and increasing salinization, as well as the growing number and impact of pest insects and diseases. Notably, microbial pathogens are exhibiting adaptability to existing treatments, which leads to a sharp decline in the production rates of food and feed products.

The taxonomy of entomopathogenic fungi includes over 100 orders and more than 700 species, such as Oomycetes, Chytridiomycota, Microsporidia, Entomophthoromycota, Basidiomycota, and Ascomycota [Sharma et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2017; Xie et al., 2019]. Among

them, the most widely used fungi in biopesticide production are *Beauveria bassiana*, *Metarhizium anisopliae*, *Isaria fumosorosea* (*Paecilomyces fumosoroseus*), *Lecanicillium lecanii* (*Verticillium lecanii*), and *Purpureocillium lilacinum* (*Paecilomyces lilacinus*) [Xie et al., 2019; Park et al., 2012; Sasan et al., 2012].

An important feature of entomopathogenic fungi is their ability to colonize the plant rhizosphere, stimulating plant growth and development [Venkatesh et al., 2022; Yinmei et al., 2022]. Furthermore, scientific sources highlight the increasing role of fungi in sustainable agriculture and global food security, as well as updated descriptions of fungal and fungus-like taxa as of 2024, indicating new prospects for fungal applications in agriculture [Manawasinghe et al., 2025; Hyde et al., 2024].

The prospects of using fungi in agriculture are evaluated based on several factors. These include their ability to promote plant growth [Hossain et al., 2017; 2020; Thambugala et al., 2020], enhance tolerance to various stress factors, and provide protection against phytopathogenic microbes and pest insects [Thambugala et al., 2020, 2022; Adedayo et al., 2023]. In addition, fungi are highly valued for their bioremediation properties, such as mitigating stress factors in soil environments—including reducing mineral depletion, decomposing heavy metals, and converting salts into plant-available forms [Kim et al., 2013; Baron et al., 2018, 2021].

Literature Review

Microbial fertilizers based on fungi. Microbial fertilizers derived from fungi serve as a primary source of essential elements (nitrogen fixation, phosphorus mobilization, and destructors of N, P, K, and microelements) [Sánchez-Esteve et al., 2016; Itelima et al., 2018; Gulshan et al., 2024; Ortiz et al., 2022; Panda, 2022; Kumar et al., 2023]. They exist in various forms, including liquid, dry, and paste-like (e.g., Agright™; BioFert; Green Awamori; JumpStart; Shayona; Rootnet; MnSol B; JumpStart) [Sheoran et al., 2013; Leggett et al., 2015; Sánchez-Esteve et al., 2016; Gómez-Muñoz et al., 2018; Simpson et al., 2020; Geethalakshmi et al., 2021]. Application methods differ, including seed treatment, root application, and foliar spraying, and they are environmentally friendly—minimizing chemical fertilizer use and soil degradation, harmless to warm-blooded animals, and able to decompose complex substances such as lignin, cellulose, and phosphorus [Kjøller et al., 2002; Pritsch et al., 2011; El-Gendi et al., 2021; McKelvey et al., 2011]—while remaining cost-effective alternatives to chemical agents [Itelima et al., 2018; Ortiz-Urquiza, 2021; Gulshan et al., 2022; Ortiz et al., 2022].

Despite their advantages, there are several challenges in using entomopathogenic fungi as insecticidal, antifungal, antibacterial, or plant growth-promoting biopreparations:

1. Fungal spores require specific environmental conditions (moisture, pH) and time for development and effective action, which leads some farmers to consider them less effective than chemical fertilizers, as fungal-based biopreparations generally act slower [Hernández-Fernández et al., 2021; Ferreyra-Suarez et al., 2024].

2. Industrial production of fungal biopreparations requires complex technological processes to maintain the required concentration of cells/spores. The presence of other microbial species in the soil can reduce the effectiveness of the target biopreparation due to competitive interactions [Chakraborty et al., 2021; Čaušević et al., 2024; Kong et al., 2024].

3. Ecological awareness, selective activity, and proper application of biopreparations are hindered by insufficient farmer education and slow adoption of modern agricultural information technologies, slowing market growth compared to chemical agents [Bagga et al., 2024; Fadiji et al., 2024; Mouratiadou et al., 2023].

4. Lack of state support for production and commercialization, insufficient regulatory control, and poor quality monitoring lead to biopreparation adulteration and reduced effectiveness [Khobragade et al., 2024; Acharya et al., 2020; Atieno et al., 2020; Yadav et al., 2024a,b,c].

5. Biopreparations are often formulated for only one or a few plant/pest species, and incorrect storage or application practices by end-users reduce their effectiveness. Training sales personnel and educating farmers are crucial for improving adoption and market competitiveness.

6. Manufacturers are not fully implementing advanced production technologies, including stabilizing microbial viability under field conditions. Innovative carriers such as nanocoatings and biochars, which enhance survival in adverse soil conditions, are underutilized [Minkosse et al., 2023; Neuberger et al., 2024; Brondi et al., 2022, 2025; Manawasinghe et al., 2025]. Combining endophytic fungi with nitrogen-fixing rhizosphere bacteria can improve efficacy [Singh et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023; Rodríguez et al., 2023].

7. Genetic engineering approaches such as CRISPR-Cas9 have begun to improve stress tolerance, symbiotic efficiency, and metabolic activity of target microbes [Peng et al., 2022a,b; Yang et al., 2024; Ma et al., 2025], yet large-scale industrial application of genetically modified strains remains limited due to concerns about unexpected mutations and metabolite production.

Research Methodology. Research on the production and practical application of biopesticides was conducted based on global market analyses and projections up to 2030 from leading economic research centers, including Markets and Markets (MM), Fortune Business Insights (FBI), Precedence Research (PR), Market Analysis Report (MAR), and Global Market Insights (GMI). Additionally, analyses were performed using open scientific databases such as Scopus, WoS, PubMed, Lens, PubMed Abstract, CrossRef, and Google Scholar.

Analysis and Results

The Significance of Entomopathogenic Fungi as Protective Agents. Fungi-based biocontrol agents have several advantages. In addition to their entomopathogenic effects against insect pests [Peng et al., 2021; Hyde et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2024], they are distinguished by their antifungal, antibacterial [Dara, 2019a; Pérez-Pizá et al., 2024; Liao et al., 2025], nematocidal [Berhanu et al., 2024], and bioherbicidal activities against weeds [Htet et al., 2022] [Ayaz et al., 2023; Chaudhary et al., 2024]. They are also noted as environmentally sustainable biopreparations that mitigate chemical resistance [Rauf, 2024; Wang et al., 2024; Diepenbrock et al., 2024] and prevent soil and water pollution [Chaudhary et al., 2024; Diepenbrock et al., 2023; Ranadev et al., 2025; Saminathan et al., 2025].

The mechanism of action of entomopathogenic fungi is mainly explained by antagonism (antibiotics, siderophores, pH changes, etc.) [Avis et al., 2001; Ansari et al., 2005; Vinale et al., 2008], mycoparasitism [Németh et al., 1991; Howell, 2003], hyperparasitism [Askary et al., 1998; Whipps et al., 2008; Benhamou et al., 2012], competition for nutrients with other microbes, insects, and nematodes [Alabouvette et al., 2009; Pedrini, 2018; Freimoser et al., 2019; Spescha et al., 2023; Puža et al., 2023; Barszczewska et al., 2025], anabiosis [Ortiz-Urquiza et al., 2013; Zhao et al., 2016; Quesada Moraga et al., 2022; Hong et al., 2023], and endophytism [Ahsan et al., 2024].

Scientific sources indicate that for industrial cultivation of entomopathogenic fungi, both primary and secondary products are utilized [Poveda et al., 2021; Manawasinghe et al., 2025]. While wheat bran is commonly used as a widespread substrate, rice bran and milled rice are widely applied in many countries. For instance, studies conducted by Indian researchers reported higher

conidial production (25.2 ± 0.13 g/100 ml) on milled rice compared to rice bran (1.15 ± 0.1 g/100 ml) [Anitha et al., 2017].

Entomopathogenic Fungi Belonging to the Genus *Metarhizium*. The genus *Metarhizium* has been extensively studied, with species such as *M. anisopliae*, *M. guizhouense*, *M. pingshaense*, and *M. taii* being most widely examined [Bischoff et al., 2009]. Modern molecular-genetic analyses have identified around 100 species in this genus [Bischoff et al., 2009; Fernández-Bravo et al., 2021]. Overall, more than 700 species belonging to approximately 90 genera of entomopathogenic fungi have been documented as biocontrol agents against insect pests, forming the basis of commercial biopreparations. The most studied genera include *Beauveria* (*B. bassiana* (Balsamo-Crivelli) Vuillemin), *Metarhizium* (*M. anisopliae* (Metschnikoff) Sorokin), *Isaria* (*I. fumosorosea* Wize), *Lecanicillium* (*L. lecanii* (Zimmerman) Viegas), and *Hirsutella* (*H. thompsonii* Fisher) [Chen et al., 2015; Bamisile et al., 2021].

Depending on their nutrition type, entomopathogenic fungi are recommended against various pests, including arthropods [Dara, 2019], aphids, locusts, thrips [Gulzar et al., 2021], larvae [Wakil et al., 2017; Yasin et al., 2019], moths [Ali et al., 2015; Tahir et al., 2019], bees, mosquitoes, whiteflies, and fruit flies [Dong et al., 2016; Bamisile et al., 2020; Canassa et al., 2020; Usman et al., 2020]. Some studies also indicate that these fungi improve soil structure and microbiota, enhance nutrient availability and water absorption in plants, and stimulate plant immune responses [Sasan et al., 2012; Jaber et al., 2014; Behie et al., 2015; Jaber et al., 2018]. Furthermore, the use of entomopathogenic fungi in plant protection increases plant resistance to chemical pesticides [Bamisile et al., 2021]. Commonly studied targets include arthropod pests such as *Bemisia argentifolii*, *Bombyx mori*, *Brevicoryne brassicae*, *Cetonia aurata*, *Choristoneura fumiferana*, *Coptotermes formosanus*, *Culex pipiens*, *Delia antigena*, *Drosophila melanogaster*, *Empoasca vitis*, *Epilachna sparsa*, *Galleria mellonella*, *Heliothis virescens*, *Manduca sexta*, *Musca domestica*, *Myzus persicae*, *Oryctes rhinoceros*, *Otiorhynchus sulcatus*, *Phaedon cochlearia*, *Plutella xylostella*, *Rhagoletis pomonella*, *Rhopalosiphum padi*, *Schistocerca gregaria* [Pedras et al., 2002; Pedras et al., 2003].

The Role of Entomopathogenic Fungi as Biofertilizers. As previously noted, entomopathogenic fungi also act as biofertilizers. They stimulate plant growth and resistance to stress factors by producing phytohormones. For example, they synthesize auxins [Dutta et al., 2014], gibberellic acid [Khan et al., 2014], cytokinins [Kang et al., 2012], and indole acetic acid [Gao et al., 2017], thereby enhancing metabolic processes, activating cell division, promoting root and lateral root development, accelerating seed germination, regulating pigment production, and optimizing photosynthesis [Gao et al., 2017; Bamisile et al., 2021].

Safety Aspects of Using Entomopathogenic Fungi. The increasing diversity of insect pests and saturation of soil microbiota with phytopathogens reduces crop yields by up to 50%, which in turn increases reliance on chemical pesticides. Chemical pesticides negatively affect the environment, soil composition, and human health, causing allergies, blood disorders, infectious diseases, and immune deficiencies, as well as reducing the export potential of agricultural products.

However, several issues remain regarding the use of entomopathogenic fungi in agriculture [Smagghe et al., 2023; Vivekanandhan et al., 2024a; Shahbaz et al., 2024]. Their widespread dissemination in the environment may lead to unintended consequences beyond their insecticidal and biofertilizer benefits [Kumar et al., 2024; Vivekanandhan et al., 2024b]. Direct application to crops may result in fungal spores (blastospores, conidia) being incorporated into the produce,

potentially producing metabolites that can induce allergic reactions in humans [Zimmermann, 2007].

For example, *Metarhizium* species synthesize six types of destruxins (A, B, E, A1, A2, B1) and cytochalasins (C and D) [Zimmermann, 2007; Strasser et al., 2000; Vey et al., 2000]. Additionally, the FKI-1079 strain of *M. sp.* produces novel insecticidal antibiotics, hydroxyfungerin A and B, which exhibit inhibitory activity against brine shrimp (*Artemia salina*) [Uchida et al., 2005]. Fermentation extracts of *M. anisopliae* also yield two new mutagenic metabolites, NG-391 and NG-393 [Krasnoff et al., 2006].

The production of destruxins depends on cultivation conditions, substrate composition, culture form (liquid or solid), and storage methods. Most studies report increased destruxin production in peptone- and rice-based media, while no destruxins were detected on Czapek-Dox solid medium [Wang et al., 2004]. Moreover, the amount of destruxin produced does not necessarily correlate with the insecticidal activity of *M. anisopliae*, indicating that destruxins are not the sole determinant of pathogenicity [Amiri-Besheli et al., 2000; Wang et al., 2004; Zimmermann, 2007]. Therefore, one of the most reliable safety aspects is that entomopathogenic fungi naturally synthesize toxins in very low amounts, posing negligible risk of toxicity.

Furthermore, the interactions of entomopathogenic fungi with symbiotic soil bacteria, beneficial microbiota, and antagonistic microbes remain incompletely understood. Environmental factors such as soil moisture, temperature, and nutrient availability directly affect the efficacy of biopreparations, limiting their effectiveness. Therefore, utilizing secondary rather than primary products of entomopathogenic fungi may offer a safer and more efficient approach.

Studies have shown that volatile organic compounds from *B. bassiana* and microorganisms such as *Bacillus subtilis*, *B. methylotrophicus*, *Pseudomonas stutzeri*, *Arthrobacter agilis*, *Trichoderma atroviride*, and *Cladosporium halotolerans*—including 2,3-butanediol, acetoin, dimethylsulfide, C16-dimethylamine, 6-pentyl-2H-pyran-6-one, and 3-methylbutanol—can act as elicitors that promote plant growth and protect against phytopathogens. Moreover, combined application of *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* exhibits high activity against *Spodoptera frugiperda* larvae, enhances cucumber growth and biochemical composition, and prevents root rot (*Rhizoctonia solani*) [Adame-Garnica et al., 2026]. Additionally, *B. bassiana* and *Trichoderma atroviride* synthesize 3-methylbutanol, which shows activity against insect pests and phytopathogens [Batool et al., 2020].

Conclusion

The global biopesticide market reached USD 2.6 billion in 2021, USD 2.9 billion in 2022, USD 3.2 billion in 2023, USD 3.5 billion in 2024, and USD 6.72 billion in 2025, and it is projected to reach USD 7.46 billion in 2026. According to leading global analytical centers, the size of the global biopesticide market, based on FBI statistics, was USD 3.72 billion in 2024, USD 9.31 billion in 2025, and is expected to reach USD 11.48 billion in 2026, growing to USD 40.61 billion by 2034, with an expected compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 17.1% [FBI, 2026].

FBI statistics indicate that in 2025, the North American biopesticide market dominated with a 37.56% share, with major companies such as Syngenta AG, Bayer AG, BASF SE, and Bioceres S.A. occupying leading positions in the production and sales of biopesticides. These trends highlight the relevance for Uzbekistan to expand the use of entomopathogenic fungi, promote the production of locally sourced biopreparations for the domestic market, and actively implement them in agricultural practice.

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